

Local Government in Australia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Carol Mills

Institute for Public Policy and Governance
University of Technology Sydney

Partners

**eurac
research**

Eurac Research
Institute for Comparative Federalism
Italy

LMU Munich
Research Center for Public Procurement
Law and Administrative Cooperations
Germany

Autonomous University of Madrid
Institute of Local Law
Spain

Institut für Föderalismus
Institut du Fédéralisme
Institute of Federalism
University of Fribourg
Institute of Federalism
Switzerland

NALAS
Network of Associations of Local
Authorities of South East Europe
France

ximpulse GmbH
Switzerland

KDZ
Center for Public Administration Research
Austria

Council of Europe
Congress of Local and Regional Authorities
France

University of Warsaw
Institute of Political Science
Poland

ZELS
Association of the Units of Local Self-Government
North Macedonia

University of the Western Cape
Dullah Omar Institute for Constitutional
Law, Governance and Human Rights
South Africa

Addis Ababa University
Center for Federalism and Governance Studies
Ethiopia

Universidad Nacional de General San Martín
School of Politics and Government
Argentina

SALGA
South African Local Government Association
South Africa

Jawaharlal Nehru University
India

University of Technology Sydney
Institute for Public Policy and Governance
Centre for Local Government
Australia

National University of Singapore
Centre for Asian Legal Studies
Asia Pacific Centre for Environmental Law
Singapore

University of Western Ontario
Centre for Urban Policy and Local Governance
Canada

November 2021

The Country Report on Local Government in Australia is a product of the LoGov-project: “Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay”.

The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

LICENSE

CC BY 4.0

INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

University of Technology Sydney: Carol Mills
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malferttheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Jamie Davies/Unsplash

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 823961.

Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Australia.....	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Australia: An Introduction	6
2.2. <i>Provision of Services in Regional and Rural Areas</i>	8
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Australia: An Introduction	11
3.2. <i>Limiting Rate Increases in New South Wales and Victoria</i>	13
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Australia: An Introduction	16
4.2. <i>Amalgamations in New South Wales</i>	18
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Australia: An Introduction.....	21
5.2. <i>Changes in the Structure of Intergovernmental Relations and their Implications for Local Government</i>	23
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Australia: An Introduction	26
6.2. <i>Innovative Approaches to Citizen Participation</i>	28

Structure of Local Government

4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Australia: An Introduction

Carol Mills, Institute for Public Policy and Governance, University of Technology Sydney

Reforms to Australia's local government systems over recent decades have often focused on structural change, particularly around increasing scale. For example, in the 1990s, the Victorian Government dismissed all local governments in order to redraw boundaries and drastically reduce the number of councils. It was then voted out of office as voter discontent with the swiftness of these and other dramatic reforms became a major state election issue. Similarly, in 2008, the Queensland Government halved the number of local governments and a small number of the amalgamated councils have since demerged. In 2015-16, the New South Wales Government sought to reduce the number of local governments but the reform process remained incomplete. It was abruptly halted due to a mix of local community discontent (although the amalgamations in metropolitan areas were largely supported by the wider community), a change of state political leadership, and court challenges by a small number of local governments faced with merger. Despite these challenges in May 2019, 42 councils in NSW were merged into 19 organisations.

The driving force behind these moves to structural reform has largely been ideological, the notion being that smaller local governments are less efficient. While all local government reform to date has been 'done to' local government, it is interesting to note the reluctance or perhaps inability for significant self-initiated reform by the sector. Despite advanced financial modelling and optimistic projections, there is currently no Australian evidence to support the claims that larger local governments are necessarily more efficient. This is a topic currently being explored by the Institute for Public Policy and Governance of the University of Technology Sydney. There is more evidence that larger local governments can promote strengthened strategic leadership capacity but this has been difficult to measure and warrants further research.

It is important to note that not all of Australia's territory is covered by local government. Some remote 'unincorporated' areas are administered by state and territory governments, and the Australian Capital Territory – the home of Australia's national capital – does not have a formal system of local government and local services are delivered by the Territory Government.

As for cooperation between local governments, councils in most jurisdictions form regional governance collaborative structures, either voluntarily or through incentivisation. These generally come together on a sub-regional scale to share service delivery, for advocacy or strategic planning. In 2017 legislation was introduced in New South Wales (NSW) for Joint Organisations of councils in non-metropolitan areas, facilitating the establishment of regional strategic priorities, regional leadership and intergovernmental cooperation.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Burdess N and O'Toole K, 'Elections And Representation in Local Government: A Victorian Case Study' (2004) 63 Australian Journal of Public Administration 66
<<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8500.2004.00379.x>>

Drew J, Kortt MA and Dollery B, 'Economies of Scale and Local Government Expenditure: Evidence From Australia' (2014) 46 Administration & Society 632
<<https://doi.org/10.1177/0095399712469191>>

Independent Local Government Review Panel, 'Service Delivery and Infrastructure: Background Paper' (Report prepared for the NSW Government, 2012)

UTS IPPG, 'Why Local Government Matters' (UTS) <<https://www.uts.edu.au/research-and-teaching/our-research/institute-public-policy-and-governance/about-institute/ace/g/why-local-government>>

Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020 re-
search and innovation programme under
grant agreement No 823961.

